

NOTES

Diosgenin from *Solanum* Species

Sipra Mookherjea and Rebecca Mathew

Occurrence of diosgenin with solasodine in plants belonging to the genus *Solanum* was first reported by Sato *et al.*¹ in 1953. Thereafter several workers have reported similar association of diosgenin with solasodine in a number of solanum species²⁻⁴. We have earlier reported three rich sources of solasodine⁵⁻⁶ in the berries of *S. khasianum* Clarke, *S. elaeagnifolium* Cav. and *S. auriculatum* Ait. Herein we report diosgenin from these sources. Berries of *S. elaeagnifolium* and *S. auriculatum* contain 0.55% and 0.01% diosgenin. *S. khasianum*, however contains very little diosgenin.

EXPERIMENTAL

The finely ground dry fruits (1.4 kg.) of *S. elaeagnifolium* were extracted in a Soxhlet extractor with petroleum ether 60°-80° (4 l) for 40 hr, then with alcohol (4 l) for 100 hr. The alcohol extract was mixed with conc. hydrochloric acid (800 ml.) and the mixture was refluxed on water bath for 6 hr. The alcohol was distilled off after addition of water. The solid precipitate was filtered and the residue was washed and dried.

The solid material (86 g.) thus obtained was extracted with benzene (300 ml.) in a Soxhlet for 35 hr. On evaporation of this benzene extract 14 g. of solid was obtained. This was subjected to chromatographic resolution over a column of neutral alumina. Three fractions were obtained. The first fraction came with petroleum ether : benzene (3 : 1), the second with benzene and the third with benzene : chloroform (3 : 1). First and third fractions were identified as solasodiene and solasodine. The second fraction (0.78 g.) was crystallised from alcohol in plates m.p. 205°-206°. With acetic anhydride and pyridine it gave a crystalline acetate m.p. 195°-197°.

Both the original compound and the acetate did not depress the m.ps. of authentic diosgenin and diosgenin acetate, when mixed together. Their identity was also established by thin layer chromatography.

1. Y. Sato and H. G. Lantham, (Jr.), *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 6067.
2. H. Sander, *Naturwiss.*, 1961, **48**, 303.
3. Schreiber, H. Kand Roensch, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1965, **298**, 285.
4. O. S. Madaeva and L. F. Stepanova, *Med. Prom. SSSR*, 1965, **19**(3), 49.
5. P. C. Maiti, S. Mookherjea and R. Mathew, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1965, **54**, 1828.
6. P. C. Maiti and R. Mathew, *Curr. Sci.*, 1967, **36**, 1261.

Thus the second fraction was identified as diosgenin, the yield being 0.555% on the basis of dry weight of fruits.

Similarly, diosgenin was isolated from the fruits of *S. auriculatum* Ait. in 0.012% yield on the basis of dry weight of fruits.

We gratefully acknowledge the financial assistance obtained from P.L. 480 Fund, U.S.D.A.

Botanical Survey of India,
76, Acharyya J. C. Bose Road,
Calcutta-14.

Received February 14, 1969.